

Scope Definition Checklist

Project:

Responsible:

Date:

Question	Compliance	Comments
1. Is the main deliverable clearly defined, including objectives and core functionalities?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2. Are out-of-scope elements identified to avoid ambiguity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3. Have the stakeholders and end-users been identified, and are their needs considered?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
4. Are the expected benefits (economic, operational, or strategic) clearly stated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
5. Have all technical, legal, operational, financial, and timeline constraints been identified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
6. Are system integrations and required interfaces specified or planned?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
7. Does the scope include performance, reliability, or other critical quality requirements?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
8. Has the scope's technical, operational, and economic feasibility been evaluated by the team?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
9. Is the scope aligned with business goals and validated by stakeholders?	<input type="checkbox"/>	
10. Are there measurable criteria to define project success and acceptance?	<input type="checkbox"/>	